

metry^{4,5}, HPLC⁶⁻¹³, HPTLC^{14,15} alone or in combination with other drugs. BISO can be determined by spectrophotometry^{16,17}, HPLC¹⁸⁻²⁰, LCMS^{21,22} and HPTLC^{23,24} as alone or in combination with other drugs. To the best of author's knowledge, there are a very few reported method for their simultaneous analysis by HPLC²⁵ method. So, the aim of this work has to develop a recently new, simple, sensitive and validated HPLC chromatographic method for the simultaneous determination of AML and BISO in their pure powdered form, laboratory prepared mixtures and in their pharmaceutical tablet dosage form. The developed methods can be successfully applied in routine analysis and quality control laboratories.

Materials and methods :

Reagents :

An analytical pure sample of Amlodipine besylate (AML) and Bisoprolol fumarate (BISO) were procured as a gift samples from Wockhardt Pvt. Ltd., Aurangabad, Maharashtra (India). The combination tablets of AML and BISO were collected from retailer, Aurangabad, Maharashtra (India).

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade and purchased from Qualigens Fine Chemicals (Mumbai, India), HPLC grade methanol and acetonitrile were purchased from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). Milli-Q/HPLC water was used for the preparation of buffer and other aqueous solutions.

Instrumentation :

Chromatographic separation of AML and BISO was performed on Sil C-18 HS (KYA TECH, Japan) column having 250 × 4.6 mm ID and 10 μm particle size. The liquid chromatographic system consists of following components : Jasco HPLC model containing PU 2080 Plus Intelligent HPLC pump, Jasco UV 2075 Plus Intelligent UV-Vis Detector and Rheodyne injector (7725i) with 20 μL fixed loop. A Borwin chromatography software was used for data acquisition and evaluation. The Shimadzu electronic micro balance was used for weighing purpose. A Elder pH meter connected with a PPL CL-51BpH electrode was used to measure the pH of the aqueous mobile phase. Microsoft Excel 2007 was used to calculate matrices and *p* values of the regression coefficients.

Preparation of buffer (pH 3.0 ± 0.05) :

Weigh about 3.1 g and dissolve potassium dihydrogen

phosphate dihydrate in 900 ml of distilled water, adjust the pH to 3.0 with 10% *o*-phosphoric acid and add sufficient water to produce 1000 ml.

Preparation of mobile phase :

A mixture of methanol, acetonitrile and 50 Mm potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer (25 : 30 : 45 v/v/v, pH 3.0 adjusted with 10% *o*-phosphoric acid) was used as mobile phase. Sonicate and filter the mobile phase through 0.45 μm or finer porosity membrane and degas. Use mobile phase as a diluents and blank.

Preparation of rinsing solvent :

A mixture composed of acetonitrile and water in a proportion of 40 : 60 % v/v used as a rising solvent.

Standard preparation of AML and BISO solution :

A stock solution containing 1000 μg/ml of AML and BISO were prepared separately by dissolving AML and BISO in methanol. A working standard solution containing 10–100 μg/ml AML and BISO were prepared from the above stock.

Sample preparation :

From stock AML and BISO standard solutions (1000 μg/ml), pipette out 10 ml into 100 ml volumetric flask individually and dilute them with diluent to get concentration of about 100 μg/ml (sub stock AML and BISO). In 100 ml volumetric flask, pipette out individually 10 ml of sub stock AML and BISO solution and dilute it upto the mark with diluent to get concentration of about 20 μg/ml of AML and BISO individually.

Determination of λ_{max} of AML and BISO :

The λ_{max} of sample solution of AML and BISO (20 μg/ml) was determined on Shimadzu UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Model UV-1800) in the range 200–400 nm using mobile phase as blank. The isopiestic point of sample of AML and BISO solution was found to be maxima at about 267 nm (Fig. 3).

Selection of chromatographic method :

Proper selection of the method depends upon the nature of the sample, molecular weight and solubility. The drug selected for the present study was polar and separated by reverse phase chromatography. C₁₈ column was chosen as stationary phase and a mixture of methanol : acetonitrile : 50 Mm potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer (pH 3.0) is adjusted with 10% *o*-phosphoric acid

Fig. 3. UV absorption spectrum of AML and BISO laboratory mixture.

in the ratio of 25 : 30 : 45 v/v/v used as mobile phase. Then it was proceeded with different ratios of mobile phase.

Chromatographic condition :

A reverse phase C-18 column, equilibrated with mobile phase a mixture of methanol : acetonitrile : 50 Mm potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer (pH 3.0) is adjusted with 10% *o*-phosphoric acid in the ratio of 25 : 30 : 45 v/v/v was used. The active principle was eluted isocratically and the mobile phase flow rate was maintained at 1.0 ml/min. The effluents were monitored at 267 nm with the detector. The sample was injected using a 20 μ L fixed loop and the total run time was 10 min. Separately inject 20 μ L of the blank solution (one injection) and standard sample preparation (in duplicate) into the chromatograph, record the chromatograms and measure area counts for Fig. 4 have shown the chromatogram for sample of AML and BISO by RP-HPLC method.

Fig. 4. Chromatogram shows separation of the two drugs AML and BISO.

Method validation :

Stability :

In order to demonstrate the stability of the standard solution of AML and BISO during analysis, the solution was stored over a period of 24 h at room temperature and then analyzed.

System suitability :

System suitability is a pharmacopeial requirement and is used to verify, whether the resolution and reproducibility of the chromatographic system are adequate for analysis to be done. The tests were performed by collecting data from five replicate injections of standards solutions.

Specificity :

Specificity was measured as ability of the proposed method to obtain well separated peak without any interference from component of matrix. Peak purity of AML and BISO was assessed to evaluate the specificity of the method. The sample and standard chromatograms were scanned at three different levels, i.e. peak start (S), peak apex (M) and peak end (E) positions. The specificity of the RP-HPLC method was determined by comparison of the chromatogram of standard and sample solution. Mean retention time was found to be for AML 3.34 min and for BISO 7.63 min.

Linearity of the calibration line :

From the stock solution of AML and BISO, prepare the dilutions over concentration range of 10–100 μ g/ml. These solutions were injected in to HPLC system as per test procedure and recorded the area under curve. A peak area was plotted against the corresponding concentration of the drugs as shown in Figs. 5 and 6.

Precision :

Intraday precision of test method is demonstrated by three injections of the same batch (same concentration) of samples at initial, 3 and 6 h (Table 2). Interday precision of test method is demonstrated by three injections of the same batch (same concentration) of samples on three successive days viz. 0, 24 and 48 h (Table 2).

Accuracy :

Accuracy was ascertained on the basis of recovery studies performed by standard addition method. It was assessed by determination of the recovery of AML and

Table 1. System suitability data of AML and BISO by RP-HPLC method

Sr. No.	Peak area		Asymmetry		Selectivity	Retention time		Resolution	No. of theoretical plates		Capacity factor	
	AML	BISO	AML	BISO		AML	BISO		AML	BISO	AML	BISO
1.	348115	492120	1.21	1.6	2.9	3.34	7.63	14.06	3100	6803	2.036	5.94
2.	348170	492125	1.21	1.58	3	3.32	7.65	14.19	3060	6803	2.018	5.95
3.	348140	492080	1.19	1.6	3	3.34	7.63	14.06	3100	6803	2.036	5.94
4.	348107	492040	1.19	1.56	2.9	3.35	7.62	14	3118	6783	2.045	5.93
5.	348125	492046	1.21	1.58	2.9	3.32	7.63	14.13	3060	6803	2.018	5.94
Mean	348132	492082	1.2	1.58	2.9	3.34	7.63	14.1	3088	6799	2.03	5.94
± S.D.	25.083	39.861	0.011	0.02	0	0.01	0.01	0.07	26.1	8.85	0.012	0.01
%RSD	0.0072	0.008	0.908	1.06	1.3	0.4	0.14	0.52	0.85	0.13	0.591	0.11

Fig. 5. Linearity curve of AML.

Fig. 6. Linearity curve of BISO.

BISO at three levels of concentrations (80%, 100% and 120%) by addition of known amount of standard to the placebo. Solutions were prepared in triplicate and analyzed. It was determined and expressed as percentage recovery (Table 3).

Ruggedness :

Ruggedness is the degree of reproducibility of the results obtained under a variety of conditions. It is checked that the results are reproducible under differences in conditions, analysts and instruments. It was tested on the second HPLC column of the same type by determining linearity, precision and accuracy.

Linearity was performed at six concentration points for AML and BISO in the concentration range from 10–100 µg/ml. The regression equation for AML and BISO were $y = 17482x$ with the correlation coefficient 0.9998 and $y = 24847x$ with the correlation coefficient 0.9977 respectively.

Intraday precision and accuracy were determined by measuring three series of quality control samples. Relative standard deviations at all three concentrations studied for AML and BISO were less than 2%. The relative

Table 2. Intraday-interday precision data of AML and BISO by RP-HPLC method

Parameters	Intraday precision (AML)		Intraday precision (BISO)		Parameters	Interday precision (AML)		Interday precision (BISO)	
	Area (cm ²)	% Label claim	Area (cm ²)	% Label claim		Area (cm ²)	% Label claim	Area (cm ²)	% Label claim
duration (h)					duration (h)				
0	348150	99.59	491501	99.87	0	348150	99.59	492150	99.77
3	346055	99.89	491425	99.85	24	346055	99.89	491160	99.89
6	346337	99.96	491285	99.82	48	346337	99.96	492160	100
Average		99.81		99.84	Average		99.7		99.88
± SD		0.1966		0.0251	± SD		0.2641		0.115
% RSD		0.0139		0.0151	RSD		0.1648		0.1151

Table 3. Accuracy data of AML and BISO by RP-HPLC method

Sr. No.	Standard peak area		% of pure drugs added	Peak area of sample		% Recovery		Mean		±S.D.		% RSD	
	AML	BISO		AML	BISO	AML	BISO	AML	BISO	AML	BISO	AML	BISO
1.			80	415017	589260	99.63	99.4						
2.	348180	492138	100	433765	614047	99.91	99.83	99.73	99.7	0.156	0.267	0.16	0.2681
3.			120	449871	638508	99.65	99.89						

error ranged from 0.9 to 1.0% of the nominal concentrations of AML and BISO. As it can be seen, the results of this assessment are very similar to those obtained by the previous AML and BISO on the first investigation column.

The sample solution was prepared by two different analysts and same procedure was followed as described earlier. The % label claim was calculated as done in marketed formulation estimation as shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Result and statistical data of different analyst study

Sr. No.	Wt. of tablet powder (mg)	Peak area of std.		Peak area of sample		% Label claim	
		AML	BISO	AML	BISO	AML	BISO
1.	149.45	348175.5	492155	346055	42110	99.65	99.99
2.	149.36	348140	492185	348075	492145	99.97	99.8
						Mean 99.81	99.89
						±S.D. 0.2263	0.1344
						% RSD 0.5267	0.7345

Assay (application of proposed method) :

Estimation of AML and BISO in laboratory mixture :

Five different laboratory mixtures of AML and BISO were prepared by appropriately weighing the quantities of drug samples so as to get the concentration of 20 µg/

ml of AML and 20 µg/ml of BISO. The peak area of standard laboratory mixture and sample laboratory mixture was compared to obtain the concentration as shown in Table 5.

Estimation of AML and BISO in tablets :

Twenty tablets were weighed and finely powdered. An accurately weighed tablet powder equivalent to 5 mg AML and BISO, was transferred to 100 ml of volumetric flask. A 50 ml of methanol was then added and contents were sonicated for 15 min. The volume was made upto the mark with methanol. The resulting solution was filtered through Whatmann filter paper No. 42. Aliquot portion was appropriately diluted with methanol to get final concentration of 20 µg/ml of AML and 20 µg/ml of BISO (sample solution). The peak area of standard and sample (tablet) was compared to obtain the concentration (Table 6).

Results

Chromatographic conditions for RP-HPLC method :

The RP-HPLC technique has been employed in the present investigation for AML and BISO in bulk and tablet dosage form as both drugs are polar in nature. During

Table 5. Statistical data for estimation of AML and BISO in laboratory mixture

Sr. no.	Weight of standard (mg)		Weight of sample (mg)		Peak area of standard		Peak area of sample		% Drug estimation	
	AML	BISO	AML	BISO	AML	BISO	AML	BISO	AML	BISO
1.			5.02	5.01			348150	492150	99.99	100
2.			5.01	5.02			348125	492135.5	99.98	99.8
3.	5.01	5.01	4.99	5.03	348160	492120.5	348185.5	492160	99.6	99.6
4.			5.03	4.99			348135	492145.5	99.99	100.4
5.			5.00	5.03			348190	492115	99.81	99.61
								Mean	99.87	99.88
								±S.D.	0.171	0.3325
								% RSD	0.271	0.3828

Table 6. Statistical data for estimation of AML and BISO in tablets

Sr. no.	Weight of standard (mg)		Weight of sample (mg)	Peak area of standard		Peak area of sample		% Drug estimation	
	AML	BISO		AML	BISO	AML	BISO	AML	BISO
1.			149.50			347012	491050	99.89	99.83
2.			149.45			345848	491238	99.6	99.87
3.	5.02	5.02	149.45	348175.0	492138.5	346055	491160	99.65	99.89
4.			149.40			346337	491035	99.8	100.03
5.			149.45			345459	491180	99.47	99.45
							Mean	99.68	99.81
							±S.D.	0.166	0.217
							% RSD	0.296	0.3974

selection and optimization of the mobile phase it was observed that the retention time of the analysis is decreased with increased in the proportion of organic modifier like acetonitrile in the mobile phase. The sharpness of the peak is achieved with increasing the proportion of acetonitrile whereas the increased proportion of aqueous resulted in broadening of the peak.

The chromatographic conditions were optimized to achieve the best resolution and peak shape for AML and BISO. During selection and optimization of the mobile phase, initially tried with acetonitrile and water combination 70 : 30, 50 : 50 and 60 : 40 at various pH 3–7 results into broadening of the peak. Phosphate buffers of pH 3.0–7.0 were tried but the peak shapes for the drugs were sufficiently symmetrical only for pH value below 4. Therefore, the addition of methanol was decided for well defined and resolved peaks with mean retention times. Thus mobile phase comprising of methanol : acetonitrile : 50 mM potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer (25 : 30 : 45 v/v/v) pH 3.0 was confirmed as it gives sharp, well resolved peaks with symmetry within limits and significant reproducible retention time for AML and BISO.

The selection of the wavelength was based on the isopiestic point of AML and BISO. The λ_{\max} obtained by scanning of standard laboratory mixture in mobile phase was found to be 267 nm. This system gave good resolution and optimum retention time with appropriate capacity factor (< 10). The mean values of system suitability test result are depicted above. After establishing the chromatographic conditions, standard laboratory mixture was prepared and analysed by following procedure described under experimental and results. As the method give accu-

rate, reliable results and therefore was extended for estimation of drugs in tablet formulation.

Method validation :

Stability and suitability :

The mixture of AML and BISO was found to be stable for one day at room temperature. From the system suitability studies it was observed that all the parameters were within limits. The RSD for the retention times of principal peak from 5 replicate injections of each standard solution was observed not more than 2.0%, the capacity factor for AML and BISO peaks was observed not more than 10% and the number of theoretical plates (N) for AML and BISO peaks was observed not less than 2000 (Table 1). Hence it was concluded that the instrument, reagents and column were suitable to perform the assay.

Specificity :

The values obtained for AML 3.35 min and for BISO 7.65 min were very close to that in laboratory mixture and tablet dosage form as compare to standard solution of AML and BISO indicates no interference from the component of matrix (Fig. 4).

Linearity :

The linearity range for AML and BISO was found to be of 10–100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ as shown in Figs. 5 and 6. The regression equation and correlation coefficient (r) obtained by least square regression method were 0.9999 and 0.9995 for AML and BISO respectively. The linearity of the calibration graph and conformity of RP-HPLC value to Beer's law were proven by the high correlation coefficients ($r^2 = 0.9999$ and 0.9995) for the regression equation, $y = 17458x$ and $y = 24453x$ for AML and BISO respectively.

Precision :

Replicate estimation of tablet analyzed by the proposed method has yielded quite consistent result indicating repeatability of method. Similarly the relative standard deviation of three replicates injections for intraday and interday precision were not more than 2.0% (Table 2).

Accuracy :

Accuracy of the proposed method was ascertained from the recovery studies by standard addition method. The mean % recovery for AML 99.73% and BISO 99.70%. The results were observed good recovery within limits (98–102%) as discussed in Table 3.

Ruggedness :

Studies were carried out only for the two different parameters like different time, different days and different analyst. Results of estimation by proposed method are very much similar under variety of conditions as estimated and shown in Table 4. This study signifies the ruggedness of the method under varying condition of its performance.

Assay :

Assay results show excellent label claim of 99.68–99.87% and 99.81–99.89% for AML and BISO respectively (Tables 5 and 6).

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